

REVIEW OF FOREIGN PRACTICE ON THE INITIATION OF CRIMINAL PROSECUTION

Khudaybergenov Bakhram Kuanishbaevich

Associate professor at Department of Criminal Procedure of
Tashkent State Institute of Law, PhD in law
Email: xudaybergenovbaxram550@gmail.ru

Annotation: The article analyzes the problems of the initial stage of criminal proceedings caused by changes in the criminal procedure legislation. Special attention is paid to improving the rules governing the procedure for conducting pre-investigation checks, as well as regulating the stage of initiation of criminal proceedings with the study of foreign experience.

Keywords: criminal proceeding, pre-trial proceedings, initiation of criminal case, verification of a report of a crime, inquirer, investigator, prosecutor's supervision.

Access to justice is a fundamental principle of the rule of law in every country. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring the right to access to justice is one of the most important procedural guarantees, the implementation of which is carried out through the unconditional and strict fulfillment of the tasks of criminal procedural legislation. It should be noted that they reflect the priority of protecting the rights and legitimate interests of persons who have suffered from criminal actions, which fully corresponds to both international legal norms and the norms enshrined in the Constitution of our country.

However, it should be noted that the regulatory framework of the initial stage of pre-trial proceedings in a criminal case and the existing practice do not fully guarantee citizens' right to access to fair justice. Unfortunately, to this day, there are documented cases of unlawful and unjustified refusals to initiate criminal proceedings, gross violations of laws. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted in a meeting on ensuring justice and combating

corruption: "... the quality of investigation and the qualification of investigators do not meet the requirements. In the first five months of this year, courts acquitted 323 citizens against whom investigative bodies made unfounded claims, and also dismissed unfounded accusations against 1854 people. In just the past year, the state paid 6.7 billion soums of material and moral damage to 236 acquitted persons"¹. Meanwhile, violations of criminal procedural law result in citizens' inability to exercise their rights to access to justice. In turn, violations of the rights and legitimate interests of individuals in criminal proceedings are most often encountered at the stage of initiating criminal proceedings. Therefore, conducting a detailed analysis of this stage regarding its problems requiring resolution using the comparative method is relevant.

Thus, the stage of initiating criminal proceedings is the most problematic and controversial in the system of stages of modern criminal procedure. Therefore, it receives increased attention from both legal scholars and legislators. Only in the last decade has the legal format of this stage undergone numerous changes. For a more in-depth study of the legal issues of the stage of initiating criminal proceedings, it is first necessary to clarify the main tasks of this stage.

The tasks of the stage of initiating criminal proceedings include, firstly, identifying the presence or absence of conditions for conducting criminal procedural activities in a criminal case; secondly, establishing grounds that under certain circumstances may exclude the proceedings in a criminal case (grounds for refusing to initiate a criminal case or for terminating an initiated criminal case). Due to the principle of publicity of criminal procedural relations, the right to make the relevant procedural decision at the stage of initiating criminal proceedings within their competence belongs to the participants in criminal proceedings on the side of the prosecution, i.e., those participants who carry out criminal prosecution in the process of proceedings in a criminal case. In addition, due to special circumstances, the right to make a procedural decision on initiating a criminal case and issuing the

¹ <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2020/06/30/justice/>

corresponding ruling belongs to certain officials.

It is precisely at the stage of initiating criminal proceedings that conditions are created for conducting investigative and other procedural actions, mechanisms for gathering evidence are determined, and the possibility of applying measures of criminal procedural coercion is assessed. We believe that the significance of the stage of initiating criminal proceedings lies in its predetermining the fate of the criminal case and all procedural activities related to the investigation of the criminal case and its substantive consideration in court. It should be noted that in recent times, serious changes have been made by the legislator to the norms of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, affecting the regulation of criminal proceedings at the initial stage of the criminal process. However, despite the special role of the initiation stage in the criminal process, some legal scholars advocate for its abolition.

Currently, many researchers recognize the institution of initiating criminal proceedings, which has been preserved in the Criminal Procedure Codes of many post-Soviet countries since ancient times, as an "exclusive" anachronism without analogues in foreign legislation, sometimes making criminal procedural activity laborious and inefficient². Nevertheless, not all scholars agree on the radical reform of this stage, considering it excessively costly³.

We believe that while the costs of restructuring pre-trial work may be significant, creating an effective mechanism for protecting individuals affected by crimes is more important in terms of the value of rights and freedoms of individuals, the protection of which cannot be compromised by expenses.

By the way, in Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Kazakhstan, after the innovations, there was no collapse of pre-trial proceedings, and the practice of applying the new provisions of the criminal procedural law has allowed to increase the protection of

² Махов В.Н. Особенности досудебного производства в уголовном процессе Российской Федерации. // Вестник Российского университета дружбы народов. Серия «Юридические науки». – 2015. – № 1. – С. 24–28;
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³ Волеводз А.Г. Упразднение стадии возбуждения уголовного дела: цена вопроса. // Уголовный процесс. – 2014. – № 1. – С. 80–83.

citizens.

Thus, the initial stage of pre-trial proceedings in a criminal case is still not free from shortcomings that create obstacles for prompt and timely response to citizens' complaints and other reasons for initiating criminal proceedings. However, in the criminal process, the efficiency of investigative activities, as the initial stage of pre-trial proceedings, is of great importance, since prompt response to each crime requires the establishment of legal regulation of criminal procedural relations, excluding prolonged examination of received statements or reports without ensuring necessary procedural guarantees for the rights of individuals participating in the verification stage.

In our opinion, abolishing the stage of initiating criminal proceedings in the criminal process of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the present time is not feasible in terms of staffing and financing of investigative activities. Therefore, during the transitional period, it is necessary to expand the list of investigative actions permitted within the framework of pre-trial verification, improve the procedure for accepting statements and reports of crimes, as well as clarify the rights of participants in pre-trial verification.

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